

An Ecocritical Reading of William Wordsworth's "Tintern Abbey"

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Abstract

Upholding Nature has become a prime concern of every person in the contemporary world. The natural calamities of late, have alarmed everyone that any human action towards destructing Nature will yield total devastation of humanity at large. Subsequently, the study of Nature has formed an integral part of various academic disciplines. The centre given to Nature in literature is conceivable in the literary theory known as 'eco-criticism'. Wordsworth's "Tintern Abbey" provides a detailed and penetrating account of the three stages of Wordsworth's attitude to Nature in the light of eco-criticism, and the depiction of the payment for love of Nature. The study focuses on an outline of eco-criticism and the intimidations, strength as well as the person being faced in the world that William Wordsworth lived in. William Wordsworth's excellent nature poem, Tintern Abbey (1798), sheds light on the way nature affects Wordsworth's memory and the ways his philosophical insights with a view, which enables him to accomplish mental growth. Through an eco-critical study of the poem, the clash between the Yale School critics, the New Historicists, and the eco-critics can be examined, and it exemplifies how the internal relationship between man and nature in Wordsworth's poem grants humanity and peace of mind. Similarly, climate change provoked alterations to the direction of waves can change how much sand they move along the coast. The foundation built on the beach, or offshore, is sensitive to these different characteristics of waves which lead to a series of menace.

Keywords: Tintern Abbey, Metamorphosis, Eco-criticism and Nature, Wordsworth, Romantic poets.

Eco-criticism is the study of the relation between environment and living organisms in their natural environment and their relationships. It also concerns man's relationships with his physical surroundings are reflected in literature. Though eco-criticism as literary theory is of current origin, the elements of it are found in the works of several journalists in the earlier period. Romanticism, in this regard, is a representation of the bare bones of eco-criticism. The Romantic poets attempted to revive the secrecy and wonder of the world and tried to institute a meaningful bond between literature and Nature. To them, Nature was the foremost cause of inspiration and pure enlightenment. William Wordsworth, who belongs to the first period of the Romantic poets, is regarded to be a Nature poet, who surveyed Nature as a living body, and believed that Nature was gifted with feeling and purpose. Wordsworth's poetry, "Tintern Abbey", which is "an auto-monologue with a setting and an auditor", is a typical

eco-critical work. Nature serves as both “a locus of imaginative energy” and “a potent source of intellectual ideas” that acts as the inspiring instrument for the Romantics. As various critics have pointed out, Wordsworth’s approach to Nature in his “Tintern Abbey” can be pigeonholed into three stages such as boyhood, youth and stage of metamorphosis which can be analysed from an ecocritical point of view.

Wordsworth, at the stage of boyhood, which is also marked as the publicity of the body, was unconscious of the value of Nature and therefore did not apprehend and acknowledge its beauty and worth. At this stage, he had only the insight judgment of the dramatic beauty of Nature, and thus, Nature did not manipulate his mind. Consequently, he could not enjoy the entertainment and happiness offered by Nature. He was filled with remorse rather than rejoice. This is visible in his poem:

“...when like a roe I bounded o’er the heights, by the sides of the dark rivers, and the empty streams, Wheresoever nature led: more like a man Climbing from something that he dreads than one Who tried the thing he loved”. In the beginning, the primeval people were very close to Nature. With the coming out of globalisation and transformation, the people in the recent past had forgotten to recognise the value of Nature and had become uninformed of its importance to their existence. Therefore, in the name of modernisation and actual progress, they had been imposing on Nature, all kinds of distress in the form of deforestation, nuclear tests, pollutions, over-use of natural resources, and so on. Consequently, Nature has begun to retort against humanity in the way of natural calamities like tsunami, earthquakes, global warming, melting of glaciers and climatic changes and it has already started to be a terror to human beings.

In his youth, which is respect as a stage of mind, Wordsworth was obsessed with the external beauty of the colours and forms of Nature. His communion with Nature had mellowed him and made him feel for the distress of his fellow beings. However, he did not rationalise at his ‘thoughtless youth’. This stage represents the present state of affairs in the world. People have become aware of the essence of Nature to their continuation, and they have obtained after the tsunami and recent climatic fluctuations that human life is not permissible outwardly Nature. However, the strengths that have been taken in the world at present are not satisfactory to protect the earth from the ecological emergency that is prevalent.

The third stage of his life is of transformation, wherein Wordsworth begins to trim down why he should feel for the distress of his fellow human beings? When he begins to downsize, he discovers that the same principle which is in him is present in all other people. In other words, there is ‘one underlying opinion’ which is pervasive in all creatures:

And I have felt

A presence that disturbs me with the joy
Of elevated thoughts; a sense sublime
Of something far more deeply interfused,
Whose dwelling is the light of setting suns,
And the round ocean and the living air,
And the blue sky, and in the mind of man:
A motion and a spirit that impels
All thinking things, all objects of all thought,
And rolls through all things.

(Green, 2007, p. 77)

Wordsworth’s connection with Nature has made him experience the unseen dogma. That is why, whenever he looks at Nature, he is reminded of the sufferings of his fellow beings, and he resents for them. Like Wordsworth, there is a need for each somebody in the present world to notice the animating code of the world, so that intimacy with Nature may be developed, and thus Nature and

humanity may be protected from all sorts of perils that would ravage them. Some critics refer to this teaching as God and relate it with pantheism. To avoid besides oppositions on this, the animating criterion could be regarded as a fundamental value and worth of Nature. Whether one considers in God or not, one cannot deny the indispensability of interrelationship between human beings and Nature. Therefore, somebody in this world is required to recognise and grasp the worth of Nature in his or her life.

The classical Cartesian dualism, Greek humanism, the Judeo-Christian concept of the great chain of 'Being' and anthropocentrism has emphasised the supremacy of humans over Nature. This feeling of superiority and command is the primary cause of environmental debasement. Wordsworth, who had encountered the divine principle that seems to permeate in the entire creation, was antagonistic to the claim of human authority. This is remarkably testified by R. O. C. Winkler who, noting on the above-quoted passage, contends that "the dichotomy between the material and mental worlds which logicians had frequently taken for granted since the seventeenth century was to Wordsworth (as to Kant) wholly antipathetic, and he regularly in his verse endeavours a general statement of the basis of their unity" (as quoted in Durrant, 1970, p. 95).

Thus, Wordsworth stands as a bridge between humanity and Nature. Wordsworth's third stage of life that is portrayed in "Tintern Abbey" is symbolic of an ideal stage that is yet to be achieved. Like Wordsworth, every individual in this world should love and appreciate Nature and should recognise the divine beauty in it. Everyone should realise the essentiality of Nature in his or her life and should contribute to its protection. All the nations should make a combined effort to put an end to all that is detrimental to Nature and should go for alternative policies that would preserve both human beings as well as Nature. The civilised world must develop respect and regard for the natural world.

Throughout the poem, the light-heartedness of memories and interconnection with nature is the saviour of the poet's mind and life in the alien days of adult life clouded with early modernity. Creating a barrier between oneself and one's society is out of the question because humans are as much the product of their social surroundings as their natural environments. In this sense, nature is the negotiator that guides humans' souls and inspires the poet's creativity. Likewise, this poem unearths Wordsworth's concern about man's neglectful treatment of nature. For such eco-critics as J. Bate, J. McKusick, and K. Kroeber, the verse explains "how all parts of human nature and physical nature interactively contribute to an inclusive vitality of being multiform but not hierarchized" (qt. in Tovey 53-4). To counter, the effect of the Enlightenment models that separated humans from nature in a hierarchal tradition and brought about a gap between them whose offspring was the dominion of man over nature, Wordsworth, sought to originate a concordant relationship between humans and their environment based on holism and respect. The notion of the mastery of man over nature stems from the three convictions that consider humans superior to life: first, classical Greek humanism grants superiority to human beings over animals due to their rationality; second, the Cartesian mind/body dualism maintains that human beings, because of keeping souls, are superior to animals; and finally, the Judeo Christian notion of creation as a "Great Chain of Being," views human beings as superior to animals and plants due to the hierarchal concept that God has given man an excellent position in the "Great Chain of Being" (Britto 721-2). This single poem is an effort to counteract such beliefs and goes to great lengths to emphasise that the respectful correlation of man with nature inspires a love of self and natural surroundings that comes not only from the observation of view but also from the emotional interaction with it. If the pecking order between man and nature is abolished, or at least questioned, the division between man and nature is shattered, and a cooperative relation comes into fruition. To establish a harmonious bond between man and nature and emphasise the practical effect of the environment on man's becoming experienced.

Wordsworth sought to stress the real value of view as a result of “passionate experience”. If the observer tries to “watch and receive” nature open-heartedly, an understanding of the self and the ecological environments can be achieved. So, by rejecting socially built forms of knowledge, one can reach an in-depth experience of nature, which is not achievable “in the dull and endless strife” of book learning (Tintern Abbey 9).

Wordsworth, through the creation, “Tintern Abbey”, has shown a way to establish a better world and a better life, and has taught how a close association with Nature could be created to give birth to a peaceful and friendly presence in the world. He advises everyone to learn from the past. This is discernible in the words of Geoffrey H. Hartman (1964), who claims that “Wordsworth’s poetry looks back to look forward the better” (p. 29). Thus, the verse, “Tintern Abbey”, is a typical eco-critical work which strives to promote a relationship between Nature and human beings. It also secondhand encourages every reader to look back and see how human beings have behaved towards Creation in the past, and what the outgrowths of their anthropocentric attitude towards Nature. It also persists on the need to take proper measures to establish harmony with Nature.

Works Cited

1. Barry, P., *Beginning theory: An introduction to literary and cultural theory*. 2017: Oxford University Press.
2. Rueckert, W., *Literature and Ecology. The ecocriticism reader: Landmarks in literary ecology*, 1996: p. 105123.
3. Bate, J., *Romantic Ecology (Routledge Revivals): Wordsworth and the Environmental Tradition*. 2013: Routledge.
4. Durrant, G., *Wordsworth and the large system: a study of Wordsworth’s poetic universe*. 1970: Cambridge University Press.